

Education Quarterly Reviews

Çarkit, Cafer, and Çohantimur, Ayşen. (2021), Examination of the 6th Grade Turkish Lesson Coursebook Texts Within the Context of the Properties of the Text. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.4 Special Issue 1: Primary and Secondary Education, 280-290.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.02.246

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Examination of the 6th Grade Turkish Lesson Coursebook Texts Within the Context of the Properties of the Text

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Abstract

In this study, the texts in the 6th-grade Turkish coursebook, prepared according to the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum, have been analysed in terms of various text types. In this framework, the texts in the book have been examined and evaluated according to the criteria of the function, literary genre, logic level, and the utilization feature in language teaching, which the researchers have created based on the literature. The case study of qualitative research methods was used in the study. The data source of the research is the 6th-grade Turkish textbook used in 2020-2021 academic year. The data of the study was obtained through document review. The data obtained in the study were analysed and evaluated by content analysis, one of the qualitative data analysis methods. The research findings determined that the book included informative texts more than narrative texts and poems in terms of their functions. It has been determined that the texts in the book show a rich variety in terms of literary genre. It has been concluded that most of the texts in the book in terms of logic level are simple texts written at the level of plain logic. In the context of their usage characteristics in language teaching, it was determined that literary texts have more place than original texts in the textbook. Based on these findings, it was concluded that sufficient attention was not given to text selection in the textbook, and suggestions for text selection were presented in the process of preparing a Turkish textbook.

Keywords: Turkish Textbook, Text, Literary Genre, Logic Level, Function

1. Introduction

Language education aims to improve students' reading, writing, listening and speaking skills. Textbooks have an important function in this process (Ensar, 2002; Arici, 2009; Woody, et al., 2010; Carkıt, 2019). As a matter of fact, the process of developing basic language skills aims to improve students' both cognitive and affective characteristics through the texts in the textbooks. In this respect, the texts in the textbooks are seen as important educational resources (Oates, 2014; Usiskin, 2013). In the Turkish teaching process, textbooks and texts in the textbooks are the main sources of reference. In this respect, it is useful to explain the text conceptually first.

The word text is originally derived from the Latin word "textus" and means "weaving, writing knitting" (Yilmaz, 2010). Based on these meanings, a text can be stated that it is a knitted and interconnected series of writings. According to Gunay (2017), a text is a language string produced verbally or in writing by one or more people in a specific communication context. According to this definition, the text is a means of communication, namely, a means of expressing emotions, thoughts and desires through language. From another point of view, the text is a language element that is a communication function, is not static but has a dynamic feature. According to Gunes (2013), it is the product that results from the construction of the message to be given with a logical arrangement in a way that creates semantic harmony. Accordingly, the text can be evaluated as a work of language that requires a mental design and creates a meaningful whole within itself. In this respect, although the text is seen as a collection of parts that compose it and carry meaning integrity, it is a language product with a richer meaning than the parts that compose it.

A text is formed by composing sentences by establishing meaningful integrity of words made up of sounds and establishing meaningful and connected paragraphs with sentences (Aktas, 2009). In this sense, the text can be likened to a chain and the words, sentences, and paragraphs that make it up to that chain's rings. One of the main features of the texts is that the elements that form them are not composed randomly but in a certain order, meaning, logic and within grammar rules. The critical thing in text organization is the unity of language, meaning, and thought between sentences and paragraphs (Musaoglu, 2003). In these respects, the text can be considered as a complex structure consisting of sound, words, sentences, and paragraphs, which are the basic elements of language in a composition.

The texts in the textbooks have special importance in language teaching because the main material of language teaching is texts (Lackie & Tarry, 1993). The texts in the textbooks contribute to the development of the cognitive, emotional, and social skills of the target audience as well as language skills. In addition, these texts play an important role in helping students gain effective communication skills. In this respect, the texts in the textbooks are used to improve the cognitive, linguistic, emotional and social skills of the students during the Turkish teaching process. For this, selecting the texts to be included in the textbooks is considered a process that requires intensive study and analysis. When the literature is examined, it is seen that the texts are subjected to various classifications in terms of genre, characteristics, and usage purposes. It is useful to explain these classifications at the point of the theoretical background of the study to be carried out in this research.

Texts are divided into various categories according to the purpose of writing, content, and language usage characteristics. Ozmen (2001) examines texts as fictional, informative, and literary texts. Cemiloglu (2015) divides texts into three categories: Texts based on events, thoughts, and feelings. Gunay (2017) classifies text types as narrative, descriptive, conversational, linguistic, proving, explanatory, educational texts. In the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum (TLC), while literary genres such as story, novel, fairy tale, biography, essay, and article are discussed at the level of classes, texts are examined under three headings as narrative, informative, and poetry. Gunes (2013) states that text types should be subjected to different classifications according to various approaches used in education. According to him, texts are examined in three categories based on their functions, characteristics in language teaching, and the level of logic.

In the literature, texts are classified as narrative, informative, and poetry according to their functions (Gunes, 2013; Cemiloglu, 2015; MoNE, 2019). Narrative texts are the ones that emerge when the writer narrates the events that have been or may be experienced in a way that affects the reader. Narrative texts enhance the reader's imagination. However, it takes the reader to different lives and offers him different experiences. Stories, novels, fairy tales, and theater texts are some of the narrative text examples (Aktas & Gunduz, 2001). On the other hand, informative texts are texts written to inform and make the reader think about any subject. These are also called didactic texts. While writing informative texts, ways of developing thought such as definition, comparison, and sampling are used. It is ensured that the reader establishes a cause-and-effect relationship. Texts in the form of interviews, travel articles, memoirs, essays, diaries, and letters are among the informative texts (Aktas & Gunduz, 2001). Another type of text, according to their functions, is poetry. Poetry is mostly texts that reflect the emotional world of the poet and have aesthetic value (Aksan, 1999).

Texts are classified as literary, produced, original and special texts according to their usage characteristics in language teaching. It is seen that the language teaching approach adopted in this classification is effective. According to Gunes (2013), literary texts are texts that emerge by expressing emotions, thoughts, and dreams aesthetically. The produced texts are written by students, teachers, and authors, and these texts generally present sections from daily life. Original and special texts, on the other hand, are texts created for communication purposes that allow the individual to express himself.

The texts are examined in two groups as simple and high-level texts in terms of logic level. According to Gunes (2013), texts written with plain logic are called simple texts, while texts created with spiral logic are called high-level or heavy texts. Simple texts are mostly texts that do not carry out an in-depth analysis that develops around a single event or situation. High-level texts, on the other hand, are texts that make in-depth analysis around multiple events and situations and put the reader into an intense thinking process.

When the literature was examined, it was found that many studies were conducted to evaluate Turkish textbooks from various angles (Kolac, 2003; Ciftci et al., 2007; Iseri, 2007; Gocer, 2008; Sahin, 2010; Durukan, 2011; Carkit, 2019). Despite this, it has been observed that sufficient studies have not been done regarding the classification of the texts in Turkish textbooks. In this sense, this study analysed the texts in the 6th-grade Turkish textbook in the context of text features. Thus, the aim was to determine the general characteristics and scope of the texts in the book. The study aims to contribute to the process of preparing textbooks and selecting text for textbooks. In this context, the following questions were sought in the research:

- What kinds of texts are included in the 6th-grade Turkish textbook in terms of their functions? Do these texts offer a balanced distribution?
- What types of literary texts are included in the 6th-grade Turkish textbook? Do these texts offer a balanced distribution?
- What kinds of texts are included in the 6th-grade Turkish textbook in terms of logic level? Do these texts offer a balanced distribution?
- Which types of texts are included in the 6th-grade Turkish textbook according to their usage characteristics in language teaching? Do these texts offer a balanced distribution?

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

The case study of qualitative research methods was used in the study. Case studies are a qualitative research method that allows one or more events, phenomena, or situations to be examined in depth and longitudinally (Davey, 1991). The purpose of case studies is to develop the proposed hypotheses instead of generalizing them (Yin, 1984). Case studies are classified in different ways in the literature. Merriam (1998) discusses case studies in 3 groups as discipline-oriented, general-purpose, and multi-case studies. In this study, the texts in the Turkish course textbook were accepted as a situation and these texts were analysed from different angles. In this respect, the study is included in the general-purpose case study. General purpose case studies allow a situation to be handled with a descriptive, interpretative and evaluative approach (Merriam, 1998). In this study, the features of the texts in the Turkish course textbook are described and evaluated.

2.2. Research Data Source

The data source of this research is the 6th-grade Turkish textbook, used at the public and private schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in 2020-2021 academic year. The said book has been prepared and published by MoNE publications. In this framework, the texts in the book have been examined and evaluated according to the criteria of the function, literary genre, logic level, and the usage feature in language teaching, which the researchers have created based on the literature.

2.3. Collection of Data

The data of the study were collected through document analysis, one of the qualitative data collection methods. Document review is a data collection method used to analyse documents with diligence and systematicity (Wach, 2013). In the field of education, many sources such as textbooks, teaching programs, student records, teacher files can be used and analysed as data sources (Bogdan & Biklen, 2007). In this research, 6th-grade Turkish Textbook is accepted as a data source and the texts in the book have been analysed by document examination. In qualitative research, long-term interaction and expert opinion are important practices that contribute to the credibility of the research (Guba & Lincoln, 1982). In the document review process, primarily in line with the criteria determined by the researchers, the texts in the 6th-grade Turkish textbook are classified, later, the obtained data were presented to two Turkish education field experts. The three texts that the researchers contradicted in terms of literary genre and two texts they contradicted in terms of logic level were included in the related categories in consensus in line with expert opinions. Besides, the data source was examined by two researchers over a period of 3 months, and the findings of the research were obtained. In this sense, it is aimed to increase the validity and reliability of the study with expert opinion and long-term interaction.

2.4. Data Analysis

The data obtained through document analysis in the research were analysed and presented with content analysis. In content analysis, the researcher presents the research pattern by presenting the findings in the context of themes and sub-themes (Patton, 2014). The aim of the researcher in content analysis is to determine the concepts and relationships that will explain the data (Yildirim & Simsek, 2016). In this study, the texts were examined according to the researchers' criteria, and the themes of the study were formed according to these criteria. In this process, in the context of research questions, the data obtained from the research on the themes of function, literary genre, level of logic, and usage characteristics in language teaching were evaluated and presented.

3. Results

In this section, the findings obtained during the study process are presented in the direction of themes and in tables. Thus, the aim was to concretize the findings obtained during the research process. Classification of the Texts in the 6th-Grade. The classification of the texts in the 6th-grade Turkish textbook in terms of their functions is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Classification of the texts in the 6th-grade Turkish course textbook in terms of their functions

Themes	Text Name	Types of Text in Terms of Function
Theme 1 Reading Culture	Text 1: This Is My Story	Informative Text
	Text 2: I'm Searching	Poetry
	Text 3: My Dear Library	Informative Text
	Text 4: Donkey with a Standing Statue	Informative Text
Theme 2 National Struggle and Ataturk	Text 1: Courage of the Turkish Soldier	Informative Text
	Text 2: Old Granny	Informative Text
	Text 3: July 15	Informative Text
	Text 4: 120	Informative Text
Theme 3 Science and Technology	Text 1: Aziz Sancar	Informative Text
	Text 2: How People Used to Measure Time?	Informative Text
	Text 3: Technology Addiction	Informative Text
	Text 4: Look, The Postman Comes with Greetings	Informative Text
Theme 4: Virtues	Text 1: Giving Means Increasing	Narrative Text
	Text 2: Caglar Asar Saya Love	Poetry
	Text 3: Silver Wing	Narrative Text
	Text 4: Heron	Narrative Text
Theme 5: Nature and Universe	Text 1: What We Are Curious About	Informative Text
	Text 2: Afyon	Informative Text
	Text 3: Water Pollution	Informative Text
	Text 4: A Life After the Snow Crystals	Informative Text
Theme 6 Our National Culture	Text 1: Anatolia	Poetry
	Text 2: The Story of Tarhana	Informative Text
	Text 3: Native Language	Poetry
	Text 4: Black Train	Poetry
Theme 7: Health and Sports	Text 1: Time for Riding a Bike	Informative Text
	Text 2: Eating, Drinking, and Digesting	Informative Text
	Text 3: 10 Questions 10 Answers About Obesity	Informative Text
	Text 4: The Story of Those Who Don't Give Up	Informative Text
Theme 8: Individual and Society	Text 1: Yes Sir	Narrative Text
	Text 2: You Do a Favour, Too	Narrative Text
	Text 3: On Friendship	Informative Text
	Text 4: Hacettepe	Narrative Text

When examining the data about text types in terms of function in table 1, it is seen that a total of 32 texts in the Turkish course textbook are distributed as five poems, six narrative texts, and 21 informative texts. The ratio of informative texts to the total number of texts is 65.62%, while the ratio of narrative texts to the total number of texts is 18.75%, and the ratio of poetry to the total number of texts is 15.62%. Accordingly, it can be stated that the texts in the book do not show a balanced distribution in terms of function, and informative texts are included more in the book. In addition, when analysed at the theme level, it was determined that the texts in the 2nd, 3rd, 5th, and 7th themes consist only of informative texts. It is thought that this situation will negatively affect the effective acquisition of the targeted objectives in the theme by the students. In the research, the texts were analysed in terms of literary genres. Findings reached in this regard are presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Classification of the texts in the 6th-grade Turkish textbook in terms of literary genre

Themes	Text Name	Literary Genres
Theme 1 Reading Culture	Text 1: This Is My Story	Essay
	Text 2: I'm Searching	Poetry
	Text 3: My Dear Library	Chat
	Text 4: Donkey with a Standing Statue	Memoir
Theme 2 National Struggle and Ataturk	Text 1: Courage of the Turkish Soldier	Memoir
	Text 2: Old Granny	Memoir
	Text 3: July 15	Notice
	Text 4: 120	Memoir
Theme 3 Science and Technology	Text 1: Aziz Sancar	Autobiography
	Text 2: How People Used to Measure Time?	Chat
	Text 3: Technology Addiction	Funny Story
	Text 4: Look, The Postman Comes with Greetings	Chat
Theme 4: Virtues	Text 1: Giving Means Increasing	Tale
	Text 2: Caglar Asar Saya Love	Poetry
	Text 3: Silver Wing	Tale
	Text 4: Heron	Fable
Theme 5: Nature and Universe	Text 1: What We Are Curious About	Funny Story
	Text 2: Afyon	Itinerary
	Text 3: Water Pollution	Article
	Text 4: A Life After the Snow Crystals	Biography
Theme 6 Our National Culture	Text 1: Anatolia	Poetry
	Text 2: The Story of Tarhana	Chat
	Text 3: Native Language	Poetry
	Text 4: Black Train	Poetry
Theme 7: Health and Sports	Text 1: Time for Riding a Bike	Essay
	Text 2: Eating, Drinking, and Digesting	Essay
	Text 3: 10 Questions 10 Answers About Obesity	Article
	Text 4: The Story of Those Who Don't Give Up	News Text
Theme 8: Individual and Society	Text 1: Yes Sir	Drama
	Text 2: You Do a Favour, Too	Tale
	Text 3: On Friendship	Chat
	Text 4: Hacettepe	Legend

When the data about the texts are examined in terms of literary genres in Table 2, It is seen that the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook is formed of five poems, five chats, four memoirs, three stories, three essays, two jokes, two articles, one statement, one autobiography, one biography, one travel article, one news text, one theater, one legend, and one fable of the 32 texts, considering the distribution of literary genres of all texts in the book, conversation and poetry have a share of 15.62%, memoirs 12.5%, story and essay 9.37%, jokes and articles 6.25%, papers, biography, autobiography, travel writing, news text, theater, legend and fables 3.12%. Conversation and poetry appear as the most used literary genre in the book. Considering the book in general, the diversity in terms of literary genre draws attention. This situation is important for students to recognize different literary genres and to perform applications on these literary genres. In the research process, the texts were analysed in terms of logic level. Relevant findings are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Classification of the texts in the 6th-grade Turkish course textbook in terms of logic level

Themes	Text Name	Texts in Terms of Logic
Theme 1 Reading Culture	Text 1: This Is My Story	Simple Text
	Text 2: I'm Searching	High Level Text
	Text 3: My Dear Library	Simple Text
	Text 4: Donkey with a Standing Statue	Simple Text
Theme 2 National Struggle and Ataturk	Text 1: Courage of the Turkish Soldier	Simple Text
	Text 2: Old Granny	Simple Text
	Text 3: July 15	High Level Text
	Text 4: 120	High Level Text
Theme 3 Science and Technology	Text 1: Aziz Sancar	High Level Text
	Text 2: How People Used to Measure Time?	High Level Text
	Text 3: Technology Addiction	Simple Text
	Text 4: Look, The Postman Comes with Greetings	Simple Text
Theme 4: Virtues	Text 1: Giving Means Increasing	Simple Text
	Text 2: Caglar Asar Saya Love	Simple Text
	Text 3: Silver Wing	Simple Text
	Text 4: Heron	Simple Text
Theme 5: Nature and Universe	Text 1: What We Are Curious About	High Level Text
	Text 2: Afyon	Simple Text
	Text 3: Water Pollution	Simple Text
	Text 4: A Life After the Snow Crystals	Simple Text
Theme 6 Our National Culture	Text 1: Anatolia	Simple Text
	Text 2: The Story of Tarhana	Simple Text
	Text 3: Native Language	High Level Text
	Text 4: Black Train	Simple Text
Theme 7: Health and Sports	Text 1: Time for Riding a Bike	High Level Text
	Text 2: Eating, Drinking, and Digesting	High Level Text
	Text 3: 10 Questions 10 Answers About Obesity	Simple Text
	Text 4: The Story of Those Who Don't Give Up	Simple Text
Theme 8: Individual and Society	Text 1: Yes Sir	Simple Text
	Text 2: You Do a Favour, Too	Simple Text
	Text 3: On Friendship	Simple Text
	Text 4: Hacettepe	Simple Text

When the data about the texts are examined in terms of logic level in Table 3, It is seen that there are 23 simple texts and nine high-level texts in the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook. The ratio of the number of simple texts to the texts in the book is 71.87%, while the ratio of high-level texts is 28.12%. This situation shows that the textbook is mostly prepared with simple texts. In this sense, it can be stated that high-level texts that develop around more than one event, situation, or phenomenon and mobilize students' thinking skills are not included in the book adequately. In the research, the texts were analysed in terms of their usage characteristics in language teaching. Relevant findings are presented in Table 3.

Table 4: Classification of the texts in the 6th-grade Turkish course textbook according to their usage features in language teaching

Themes	Literary Texts	Produced Texts	Original and Special Texts
Theme 1: Reading Culture	4	-	-
Theme 2: National Struggle and Ataturk	2	-	2
Theme 3: Science and Technology	3	-	1
Theme 4: Virtues	4	-	-
Theme 5: Nature and the Universe	2	-	2
Theme 6: Our National Culture	2	-	2
Theme 7: Health and Sports	-	-	4
Theme 8: Individual and Society	4	-	-

When the texts are examined according to the usage characteristics in language teaching in Table 4, it was observed that there were 21 literary texts, 11 original and special texts in the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook. The produced texts are not included at all, while the ratio of literary texts to the total number of texts is 65.62%, the ratio of original and special texts to the total number of texts is 34.37%. From this point of view, it is seen that there are more literary texts in the book.

4. Discussion

Supporting the cognitive, social, and emotional development of children, contributing to their linguistic development, and ensuring that they grow up as individuals who use the language correctly are among the aims of the Turkish course (Sever, 2013). Turkish lessons also make significant contributions to the development of students in terms of providing students with a love and culture of reading, developing high-level thinking skills, getting to know literary genres, and making applications for those genres. In order to achieve these goals, the texts in the textbooks, which are the main material of the Turkish course, must be carefully selected. In this study, the texts in the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook were examined under various themes in line with the research questions.

In the research process, the texts in the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook were analysed in terms of their functions firstly. In this sense, the book contains 32 texts in the research findings; five poems, six narrative texts and 21 informative texts were identified. These results show that there are more informative texts in the book proportionally. In this sense, it can be stated that the texts in the book do not show a balanced distribution in terms of their functions. However, in the study, it was determined that the 2nd, 3rd, 5th, and 7th themes consist only informative texts. The poetry type, which is one of the text types in terms of its functions, has been determined as the least used type in the book. However, poetry is an effective genre in creating literary and aesthetic pleasure in children. The findings of the research made by Yagmur, (2009); are in line with the findings of Solak and Yayli (2009) and Carkit (2019). It has been determined that the text types do not show a balanced distribution in terms of their functions in secondary school Turkish textbooks, which were also examined in related studies. In the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum, it has been stated that text types should be distributed in a balanced manner throughout the book in terms of their functions, although the types of text to be used in a theme are left to the author(s) of the book (MoNE, 2019). It can be stated in that in the research, the texts in the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook are not distributed as specified in the curriculum, and it is necessary to be more careful about this issue when preparing the book.

Second, in the research process, the texts in the 6th Grade Turkish textbook were analysed in terms of their functions. In this sense, research findings include five poems, five chats, four memoirs, three stories, three essays, two jokes, two articles, one statement, one autobiography, one biography, one travel article, one news text, one theater, one legend, one fable type text in the book, consisting 32 texts in total, was determined. Considering the book in general, the diversity in terms of literary genre draws attention. This situation allows students to recognize and experience language usage in various literary genres and exercise them. Thus, the wide

variety of literary texts contributes to students' use of the language in an aesthetic and effective manner. Again, texts in different literary genres support students' multidimensional development by presenting different experiences in terms of linguistic, cognitive, and affective aspects. The results obtained in the research support the results of Bas, (2003); Urundu, (2011); Ozbay and Cecen (2012) and Bulut (2020) they carried out in their studies in the literature. It was concluded that Turkish textbooks, which were also examined in related studies, show a wide variety in terms of literary genres. The wide variety of texts in the textbooks is considered very important in terms of allowing students to explore the richness of the language in different dimensions (Carkit, 2019). In this respect, it is beneficial to consider this situation during the text selection stage for the textbooks.

Third in the research process, the texts in the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook were analysed in terms of logic level. Based on Gunes (2013), texts that develop around a single event, phenomenon or situation, do not encourage students to think at a higher level, and are written in a linear and simple logic, are expressed as simple texts. On the other hand, texts that develop around more than one event, fact, or situation, encourage students to think at a higher level, and are written in a spiral logic, are determined as high-level texts. In this sense, in the research findings of the book that contains 32 texts; 23 simple texts, and nine high-level texts were identified. In this context, it can be stated that the texts in the book examined in the research do not show a balanced distribution in terms of logic level. Simple texts often cause students to think one way. On the other hand, while high-level texts provide students with a versatile and analytical perspective, they also provide their high-level thinking skills such as critical, creative, reflective, lateral thinking, and problem-solving skills. Including high-level texts in the textbooks that will enable students to develop their thinking skills at a sufficient level will enable them to acquire 21st century skills, while contributing to their success in international exams such as PISA (Dolapcioglu, 2020; Ozdemir, 2020; Carkit, 2020).

In the research process, lastly, the texts in the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook were analysed in terms of their usage characteristics in language teaching. Accordingly, the texts are classified into three categories as literary texts, produced texts, original and special texts. In this framework, 21 texts in the book are literary texts, while 11 texts show original and special text features. The produced texts are not included in the book. The texts produced are texts written for the purpose of teaching language as a reflection of the behavioural approach (Gunes, 2013). Since the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum is a program prepared in line with a constructivist approach, it is thought that the texts produced in the book prepared within the framework of this program and examined in the research are not included. Literary texts are considered important in terms of reaching students' language pleasure and using language aesthetically (Aytas, 2006). Original and special texts are texts created within the framework of the constructivist approach that allows the individual to express himself / herself (Gunes, 2013). It can be stated in the analysed book that the texts do not show a balanced distribution in terms of usage characteristics in the language teaching process. What is important in the language teaching process is to confront students with all kinds of texts that will support their linguistic, cognitive, social, and emotional development, thereby expanding their imagination and revealing their potential in using language effectively. At this point, it is thought that the texts in the textbooks, which are the main material of language teaching, should show a balanced distribution according to their usage characteristics in language teaching.

The research is a qualitative study conducted with the method of document analysis. There are some limitations to the research. The research was prepared and published by the Ministry of National Education conducted on the 6th-Grade Turkish textbook. At this point, it will be useful to examine the books prepared and published by different publishing houses and at different grade levels. Again, it is important to conduct researches on the opinions of teachers who are field practitioners in order to make healthy evaluations about the qualities of the texts in the textbooks. At this point, it is thought that both qualitative and quantitative studies will contribute to the literature.

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